

Development of a Virtual Signal Processing Pipeline for 21 cm Hydrogen Line for Radio Astronomy

A potential radio astronomy observatory and analytical research laboratory at home

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Abstract—The 21 cm spectral line arising from the hyperfine transition in neutral hydrogen (H I) serves as a cornerstone in radio astronomy, enabling the study of galactic structure and Doppler-induced velocity fields. This paper presents an analysis pipeline for processing open-source 21 cm hydrogen-line data using Python-based digital signal processing techniques. The raw spectral data, obtained from publicly available radio astronomy repositories, are pre-processed through Savitzky–Golay smoothing and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis to enhance signal visibility and extract frequency offsets. These offsets are further used to estimate line-of-sight Doppler velocities relative to the rest frequency of 1420.405 MHz. The results demonstrate that lightweight signal-processing frameworks can effectively reproduce the core steps of professional H I spectral analysis using open data, without requiring dedicated radio telescope hardware. This work bridges educational demonstration and practical data analysis, serving as a scalable template for undergraduate-level radio astronomy projects and low-cost observational research.

Index Terms—Hydrogen line, 21 cm, radio astronomy, signal processing, Doppler velocity, open data.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 21 cm spectral line of neutral hydrogen (H I) originates from the hyperfine spin-flip transition of its ground state, corresponding to a rest frequency of 1420.405 MHz. Since neutral hydrogen is the most abundant element in the interstellar medium, this emission line provides a powerful tool for mapping galactic structure, estimating radial velocities, and studying large-scale dynamics of the Milky Way and external galaxies.

Traditionally, such observations require high-sensitivity radio telescopes and low-noise receivers. However, recent open-access initiatives have made raw and processed hydrogen-line spectra publicly available, enabling independent data analysis and signal processing experiments even without physical observatory access.

This paper builds upon a prior mini-project that demonstrated the signal processing of a simulated 21 cm emission for Doppler velocity estimation. Here, we extend that framework to analyze real spectral data from open repositories using Python-based processing techniques. The objective is to demonstrate how smoothing, spectral enhancement, and

frequency-domain analysis can be applied to extract physically meaningful quantities such as Doppler shift and corresponding velocity components.

The work emphasizes accessibility and reproducibility, offering a scalable educational model that bridges practical radio astronomy and undergraduate-level signal processing.

II. THEORY OF THE 21 CM HYDROGEN LINE

A. Origin of the 21 cm Transition

Neutral hydrogen (H I) consists of a single proton and an electron, each possessing intrinsic spin and associated magnetic moments. The relative orientation of these spins gives rise to two configurations: *parallel (triplet)* and *antiparallel (singlet)*. The triplet configuration has slightly higher energy because the magnetic dipoles are aligned, while the singlet configuration is more stable [1].

The energy difference between these two hyperfine levels arises from magnetic dipole–dipole coupling and can be expressed as

$$\Delta E = \frac{8}{3} \alpha^4 g_p \frac{m_e}{m_p} m_e c^2 \quad (1)$$

where α is the fine-structure constant ($\approx 1/137$), g_p is the proton g -factor (5.585), m_e and m_p are the masses of the electron and proton respectively, and c is the speed of light. Substituting known constants gives

$$\Delta E \approx 5.874 \times 10^{-6} \text{ eV} \quad (2)$$

The corresponding photon frequency, obtained from $E = h\nu$, is

$$\nu = \frac{\Delta E}{h} = \frac{5.874 \times 10^{-6} \times 1.602 \times 10^{-19}}{6.626 \times 10^{-34}} \approx 1.4204 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz} \quad (3)$$

and the wavelength is

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{\nu} = \frac{3 \times 10^8}{1.4204 \times 10^9} = 0.21106 \text{ m} = 21.106 \text{ cm} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. A hydrogen atom with proton and electron spins aligned (top) undergoes a flip of the electron spin, resulting in emission of a photon with a 21 cm wavelength (bottom)

Thus, the 21 cm spectral line [2] results from the hyperfine spin-flip transition within the ground state of hydrogen. Although the spontaneous transition probability is extremely low ($A_{10} \approx 2.9 \times 10^{-15} \text{ s}^{-1}$), the vast abundance of hydrogen in the interstellar medium makes this emission observable by radio telescopes.

B. Astrophysical Relevance

Hydrogen constitutes nearly 75% of the baryonic matter in the universe and exists abundantly in the interstellar medium (ISM). The H I 21 cm line therefore serves as a fundamental probe of galactic structure, neutral gas distribution, and kinematics.

When a hydrogen-emitting region moves relative to the observer, the received frequency shifts according to the Doppler effect:

$$v_r = c \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_{\text{obs}}}{\nu_0} \quad (5)$$

where v_r is the radial velocity, $\nu_0 = 1420.405751 \text{ MHz}$ is the rest frequency, and ν_{obs} is the observed frequency. A redshift ($\nu_{\text{obs}} < \nu_0$) implies a receding source, while a blueshift indicates approach. Mapping these shifts across galactic coordinates enables estimation of galactic rotation curves and mass distribution.

C. Signal Detection and Processing in Radio Astronomy

A radio telescope [3] collects the faint 21 cm radiation using a parabolic dish or antenna array. The received signal—typically a few kelvins above the system noise floor—is amplified by a low-noise amplifier (LNA) to preserve signal-to-noise ratio. The amplified signal passes through bandpass

filters centered near 1420 MHz to reject out-of-band noise and interference.

The signal is then down-converted to an intermediate or baseband frequency using a local oscillator. A software-defined radio (SDR), controller, or data acquisition system digitizes this signal for digital signal processing (DSP). Operations such as the fast Fourier transform (FFT) convert the signal into a frequency spectrum, while smoothing algorithms like the Savitzky–Golay filter or Gaussian curve fitting enhance the visibility of the spectral peak. The measured offset in the line’s central frequency directly yields the Doppler velocity through the above relation.

Fig. 2. Schematic layout of a Radio Telescope setup

III. DATA ACQUISITION AND REPOSITORY ANALYSIS

A. Potential Data Sources and Formats

To extend the simulation framework to real observations, hydrogen-line spectra can be obtained from open repositories such as the Leiden/Argentine/Bonn (LAB) all-sky HI survey and the HI4PI full-sky survey. These archives provide calibrated 21 cm line intensities in FITS format, containing brightness temperature values as a function of frequency or radial velocity around the rest frequency of 1420.405751 MHz. Typical survey products offer full-sky coverage with angular resolutions on the order of $0.5\text{--}1^\circ$ and velocity resolutions of approximately 1 km/s, making them suitable candidates for validating signal-processing techniques developed in this work.

B. Proposed Data Extraction and Downconversion

FITS files from the above repositories may be read using `astropy.io.fits`. For compatibility with the current simulation grid, the spectral axis (frequency or velocity) would be converted and resampled to a common frequency grid centered on $\nu_0 = 1420.405751 \text{ MHz}$. If the survey provides a velocity axis, conversion to frequency is achieved by

$$\nu = \nu_0 \left(1 - \frac{v_r}{c} \right), \quad (6)$$

where v_r is the radial velocity in the survey’s reference frame. Resampling would interpolate the observational spectrum onto a 2048-channel grid spanning ± 200 kHz about ν_0 , and optional baseline normalization or unit conversion (e.g., brightness temperature to arbitrary units) may be applied to align observational units with the simulated signals. Anti-alias filtering and unit checks are recommended when decimating or regriding the data.

C. Proposed Integration with the Signal-Processing Pipeline

Once converted, observational spectra could be processed using the same Python pipeline developed for the simulated data. The intended workflow is:

- 1) resampled spectrum input,
- 2) Savitzky–Golay smoothing for noise reduction,
- 3) FFT computation for frequency-domain inspection,
- 4) line-center estimation on the smoothed spectrum,
- 5) Doppler velocity estimation using

$$v_r = c \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_{\text{obs}}}{\nu_0}. \quad (7)$$

This proposed integration would allow direct comparison of synthetic and empirical spectra and demonstrate the scalability of the processing framework to open-source radio astronomy datasets.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Simulation Framework and Signal Modeling

For demonstration purpose, a 21 cm hydrogen emission is modeled as a Gaussian spectral profile with configurable amplitude, linewidth, and center frequency, superimposed with additive Gaussian noise to emulate observational uncertainty. The simulator supports an optional secondary Gaussian component to emulate blended lines. The runtime display provides three synchronized views: the raw noisy spectrum, the Savitzky–Golay filtered spectrum, and the FFT magnitude for frequency-domain inspection. The simulation also computes an instantaneous Doppler velocity from the line-center offset for visualization purposes. The complete codebase for the simulator is intended for public release on the project repository.

Fig. 3. Enter Caption

B. Integration with Observational Data (Proposed)

The processing pipeline has been designed so observational spectra, once converted to the simulator grid (see Section III), can be processed without algorithmic changes. This design choice ensures method-level parity between simulated demonstrations and future empirical analyses. Key processing parameters, including Savitzky–Golay window length and polynomial order, FFT length, and resampling resolution, are exposed as configuration variables to allow tuning for different observational SNR and spectral resolutions.

C. Signal Processing Pipeline

The canonical processing [4] steps applied to both simulated and (proposed) observational spectra are:

- 1) **Smoothing:** apply Savitzky–Golay filtering to reduce high-frequency noise while preserving line shape;
- 2) **Frequency analysis:** compute the FFT of the detrended spectrum for inspection of periodic components and noise characteristics;
- 3) **Line detection:** identify the centroid or peak of the smoothed line profile to obtain ν_{obs} ;
- 4) **Velocity calculation:** compute line-of-sight velocity using the non-relativistic Doppler relation given above.

This methodology emulates the functional stages of a radio telescope backend (LNA, bandpass filtering, downconversion, ADC, DSP), while remaining entirely software based for the purposes of demonstration and validation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank the department of Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering of Sardar Patel Institute of Technology for giving out this wonderful opportunity to work on this piece of work for his Signal, Network & System course curriculum. The author would also like to express his gratitude to Prof. Shanti Swamy for guiding and introducing him to the digital twin technology which formed the foundation of this project.

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